

University of
Nottingham
UK | CHINA | MALAYSIA

UNIVERSITY OF
DELAWARE

TURNEYES 892951

RESEARCHER ANNEMARIE WALTER
OUTGOING SUPERVISOR DAVID REDLAWSK
INCOMING SUPERVISOR CEES VAN DER EIJK

REPORT 14

PRESENTATION ELECTION
CAMPAIGNS AND
DEMOCRATIC NORMS
MEETING, 12-13 DECEMBER
2023, DUBLIN, IRELAND

November 2024

The project Turning a Blind Eye to Scandal has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 892951

The University of
Nottingham

**How Voters' Multiple Identities Affect their
Response to Politicians' Moral Violations**

Annemarie Walter and David Redlawsk

The University of
Nottingham

1

Voters' Multiple Identities

- A social identity is a subjective sense of belonging to a group and an important part of people's self concept
- Social identities are acquired through inheritance, life experiences or accomplishments
- Social identities differ in internalization, i.e. the extent that they are central to people's self-concept

The University of
Nottingham

2

Maintaining a Positive Social Identity

3

- Mechanisms include biased information processing, in-group favoritism and out-group derogation in behaviours
- In-group bias is moderated by identification strength
- Social groups have their own moral principles, and a group member transgressing these threatens the group image
- People's own morality as well as judgements about other people's morality is determined by their social identity

3

Partisan Identity

4

- Partisanship and strength affects how voters perceive and respond to politicians' moral violations
- **Partisan Ingroup Bias Hypothesis (H1):** People will evaluate politicians engaged in moral violations who belong to their party (ingroup) more positively than politicians who do not (outgroup)
- **Partisan Identity Strength (H2):** The stronger people identify with their party, the greater their ingroup bias when evaluating politicians involved in moral violations

4

Moral Identity

5

- Moral identity entails the extent to which people's self-concept is organized around their moral beliefs
- People who hold a strong moral identity are more likely to interpret situations in a moral manner and act accordingly
- Moral identity mitigates in-group favoritism and out-group hostility
- **Moral Identity Strength Hypothesis (H3):** The stronger people's moral identity the more negatively they evaluate ingroup politicians involved in moral transgressions

5

Experimental Design

6

- A vignette study using a 6x3 between-subjects design embedded in a survey questionnaire administered to approximately 3000 U.S. voters and 3000 English voters
- We manipulated the moral principle violated (Care, Fairness, Loyalty, Authority and Sanctity) and added a social norm violation as a baseline
- We manipulated the partisanship of the politician in the vignette
- Data were collected in November 2020 by Dynata
- Dependent variable Likeability, 7-point scale

6

Stimulus Material

Norm violated	Vignette (non-partisan)
Care	You see a politician make fun of a constituent with mental health problems.
Fairness	You see a politician making sure that those who voted for him get first access to jobs.
Loyalty	You see a politician in your town say the neighboring town is better.
Authority	You see a politician violating safety regulations ordered by the Chief of Police at a disaster.
Sanctity	You see a politician was found having sex with a teenager.
Social	You see a politician carrying briefing papers to the capitol in a plastic grocery bag

7

Results: Hypothesis 1

- **Partisan Ingroup Bias Hypothesis (H1):** People will evaluate politicians engaged in moral violations who belong to their party (ingroup) more positively than politicians who do not (outgroup)

8

9

10

Effects of Partisan Identity Strength

11

11

Results: Hypothesis 3

12

- **Moral Identity Centrality Strength Hypothesis (H3):** The more central moral identity, the more likely people will negatively evaluate all politicians involved in moral violations, across both in- and outgroups.

12

13

14

Conclusions

15

- Both partisan identity as well as moral identity matter to how voters respond to moral violations
- We need to consider voters' multiple social show increasing ingroup bias as their internalization of partisan identity increases.

15

16

- This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 892951

16